

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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estimated using Lotka-Volterra and Jameson-effect models considering the inhibitory effect (a_{21}) of indigenous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) on *S. aureus*.

The results showed significant temperature-dependent differences in *S. aureus* and LAB growth rates and maximum concentrations. At 8°C, *S. aureus* had a lower SA_0 and SA_{max} concentration, and a slower μ_{max} SA (1.054 days⁻¹, 1.089 days⁻¹ for Lotka-Volterra and Jameson-effect models). At 37°C, *S. aureus* showed a significant increase in μ_{max} SA (14.97 days⁻¹, 22.24 days⁻¹) and an increase in SA_{max} . Although the root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) values were lower for the Lotka-Volterra model, the fact that a_{21} was not found significant at any temperature suggested that the Jameson-effect model was a more parsimonious model. Thus, square-root secondary models for the maximum growth rate of *S. aureus* and LAB were developed from the Jameson-effect fitted values; and subsequently these two relationships were validated against growth data obtained at 30 °C.

These results provide insights into the temperature-dependent growth kinetics of *S. aureus* in goat's Jben cheese, which is a first step for ensuring the safety of these regional dairy products.

Keywords: Jben cheese; Microbial modeling; Predictive microbiology; Jameson effect; Lotka-Volterra; Lactic acid bacteria

BIOPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA AGAINST LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES IN HEAT-TREATED RECONSTITUTED MILK

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Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) play an important role in fermented products, by promoting desirable organoleptic properties, and by their antimicrobial properties limiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria. The objective of this study was to determine the growth kinetics of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM) in heat-treated reconstituted milk, as affected by selected LAB strains *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* and *Loigolactobacillus coryniformis* isolated from goats' milk cheeses.

Challenge tests of each LAB strain in monoculture and in coculture with LM in milk adjusted to three initial pH levels (5.5, 6.0 and 6.5) were performed. Inoculated milk samples were left to ferment at 12°C for 8 days. A pH-driven dynamic growth model was fitted in separate to the LM and LAB experimental curves from both monoculture and coculture experiments; and a Jameson-effect growth model was fitted only to the coculture growth curves. In monoculture, *L. mesenteroides*, when compared to the other LAB strains, showed the highest growth rates at the three initial pH levels; whereas in coculture,

this strain was able to better control the growth of LM, by decreasing their growth rates [day^{-1}] to 1.469 ± 0.205 at pH 5.5; 2.293 ± 0.284 at pH 6.0 and 1.552 ± 0.132 at pH 6.5. *L. paracasei* and *L. coryniformis* strains were only able to inhibit and reduce the growth of LM at pH 5.5. In relation to the maximum concentration of LM (LMmax), *L. mesenteroides* was again the most effective at all initial pH tested. The LMmax [log CFU/ml] values were reduced to 15.05 ± 0.367 ; 16.32 ± 0.204 and 16.91 ± 0.132 at pH 5.5; 6.0 and 6.5, in comparison to the values 20.85 ± 0.060 ; 21.10 ± 0.212 and 21.31 ± 0.085 , obtained in monoculture, respectively. This indicates that this particular strain of *L. mesenteroides* has a broader and more inhibitory effect on LM growth across different pH levels, whereas *L. paracasei* and *L. coryniformis* are only effective in more acidic conditions (pH 5.5).

These research results provide valuable insights into the use of LAB as a natural biopreservative for controlling LM in dairy products, thereby enhancing food safety.

Keywords: Biopreservation; coculture; Monoculture; pH; Growth kinetics; Modelling; Predictive microbiology

Session 7: Process Control

Time: 11:30 – 12:30

Date: 5th September 2024

A DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS APPROACH TO IMPROVE THE ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF PROTEIN HYDROLYSATES

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Foodborne pathogens pose a significant risk to public health and seriously impact economy, motivating the development of effective antimicrobial strategies. In the context of increasing demand for minimally processed and environmentally friendly preservatives for food and pet food, the release of bioactive peptides through protein hydrolysis have sparked enthusiasm among the scientific community. This study focuses on determining the inhibitory effects of four food-derived protein hydrolysates on key foodborne pathogens and understanding the impact of the conditions of hydrolysis on their efficacy.

A fractional factorial design was used in a first step to screen the effects of temperature, pH, enzyme-to-substrate ratio and raw material-enzyme combinations. The impact of each factor on pathogen inhibition was assessed and ranked. Then, significant factors from the screening phase were optimized using a Box-Behnken design. This involved a three-level